

BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation

The article highlights the advantages of using the basic principles and rules of innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process of general education schools. Information about the role of information technology in conducting modern education is given.

Key words: information technology, education, presentation, multimedia, video.

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V state vydeleny preimushchestva ospolzovaniya osponnykh principov i pravil innovatsionnykh pedagogicheskikh tehnologi v obrazovatelnom procese obshcheobrazovatelnoy school. Predstavlena information about the role of information technology in modern implementation.

Key words: information technology, education, presentation, multimedia, video.

Abstract

The article highlights the advantages of using the main principles and rules of innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process of general education schools. Information about the role of information technologies in conducting modern education is presented.

Keywords : information technology, education, presentation, multimedia, video.

Introduction

The introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies into the educational process is based on certain laws and principles. Principle is derived from the Latin word "princepium", which means "basic", "initial condition", "guiding idea", "generalized requirement". Pedagogical technology principles are general standards and requirements to be followed in order to achieve high results in the implementation of the planned educational process. When determining them, the following circumstances are taken into account:

1. The goal of education that meets the requirements of the existing society;
2. Objective laws of the didactic process;
3. Conditions that implement the educational process;

MAIN PART

The principle of integrity of pedagogical technology - this principle requires taking into account that all elements of the pedagogical system are under mutual influence and interdependence when creating a technology project. That is, the strict determination of the educational goal (why? and why?), the content of the educational process (what?), the selection of organizational forms (how?), teaching methods and tools (with what?) and should help to choose, as well as allow to determine the effectiveness of the didactic process depending on the teacher's skill level.

The principle of integrity - denies that the first of the elements that make up the pedagogical technology should be updated or changed, and the rest should not be touched or reconstructed. For example, it is impossible to change the purpose of education and leave its content or teaching process in the same way. Today, profound changes and reforms are being implemented in the Republic's education system:

- First of all, the goal of education has been updated - it is necessary to form a free-thinking citizen, a well-rounded human personality.
- Secondly, this social order, in turn, causes a radical restructuring of the educational content, the creation of new textbooks and programs.
- Thirdly, the new content of education requires tools that speed up the process of delivering information to teachers within a certain time frame.

Pedagogical technologies envisage the planning of the educational process in advance and the implementation of this project in the classroom. Therefore, an important principle of pedagogical technology is the principle of planning the future educational process in advance. This, of course, requires creative activity from the teacher. The designed technology should be introduced within the time allotted to the subject of the lesson.

Study time is an important indicator in the pre-construction of pedagogical technology, and the teacher must take it into account. It is very important that the planned didactic process corresponds to the students' learning level and is understandable to everyone. Only then will the final result be achieved. The guarantee of the final result is another important principle of pedagogical technology. This concept is actually relative in nature, because it is natural that after the implementation of the structured technology, there will be certain results - students will master the learning material at different levels.

Another important principle of pedagogical technology is the principle of

completeness. The student's learning quality is determined by his learning coefficient. In the educational institutions of our country, the quality of learning of pupils (students) - if the coefficient of learning is equal to or more than 0.55, that is, if 55% of the educational material is learned, " is considered "satisfactory". In our opinion, this indicator is sufficient for the initial stages of reforming the education system.

One of the principles of pedagogical technology is the principle of flexibility. This principle somewhat expands the fields of application of pedagogical technologies. The technology designed for this or that topic should be flexible at least within the boundaries of the disciplines. The teacher will have the opportunity to replace or redesign the structure of the didactic process on the subjects of the subject in accordance with the diagnostic purpose, with little effort and time spent. Analyzing the results of scientific research by VBPespalko, B.Skinner, NDNikandrov, NFTalizina, BLFerberman and others, the following principles of pedagogical technology can be distinguished:

1. Creating a strict sequence of the system of devices that control students' cognitive activities. Controlling devices control students' cognitive activity only when pre-programmed by a pedagogue or methodologist (methodologist). Pedagogical activity is necessary to manage the situations that arise in the educational process, but are not pre-programmed. Today, creating a fully programmed e-book is currently ineffective. In managing students' cognitive activities, it is necessary for the student to design effective use of machine-assisted (automatic) and their joint and self-management types.
2. Organization of the management of the educational process in each part of the students' cognitive activity according to a closed cycle. In addition to direct information transfer to students, receiving information from them - feedback communication is taken into account. It is known from cybernetics that for the normal functioning of the control system, a correct and reversible connection must be established between the machine and the object (student). Both the teacher and the student are equally important in feedback. For the student to master the educational material, and for the teacher to analyze the mistakes made and make appropriate corrections to the pedagogical process. Feedback, which is necessary for the learner to independently make appropriate adjustments to his work, is called feedback. Due to the internal feedback, the student will have the opportunity to consciously master his knowledge and skills. In this case, no explanations, advices, referrals, etc. are allowed. It is possible to control the learning process in a cyclical manner only if external

feedback is established by the teacher.

3. Use of separate steps in the transmission of educational materials, revealing its essence. Fulfillment of these requirements ensures that the program material is comprehensible to all. Each step covers the following three interrelated parts of training content : information, feedback operation and control. The sequence of educational steps forms the basis of pedagogical technology. Students' activities in the program (each learning step) are highly individualized.

4. The fourth principle is called the individual image of mastery. Adherence to this principle ensures that all students (albeit at different times) fully master the learning material. It is necessary to choose the most suitable educational materials for each student's mental (perception, attention, thinking) development and determine the learning trajectory that suits him. will

5. Use of special technical devices in the educational process. A special technical device is a technical means that implements each learning step (information, operation, feedback, control).

CONCLUSION

The above principles determine the specific characteristics of pedagogical technology as a didactic system. However, they do not reflect all aspects related to the organization of the educational process.

Pedagogical technology, as a special case, uses traditional teaching and all the principles of didactics (consciousness and activity, demonstrability, connection of theory with practice, coherence in teaching, comprehensibility of teaching and thoroughness of knowledge). Pedagogical technology principles and general didactic principles complement and enrich each other.

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